

Solderless Fault Insertion Test Set to Enhance ATE Operator Training

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Abstract—It is the mandate of Automated Test Equipment (ATE) to minimize manual tasking and maximize automation. However, the role of the operator remains crucial to successful deployment of any ATE system. Simple tasks such as setting up the Unit Under Test (UUT), correct probing, potentiometer alignments, etc. must be taught so new operators can establish a basic level of diagnostic capability in the fleet. Current Consolidated Automated Support System (CASS) training hardware is based on F-14 and S-3 platforms which are obsolete, utilize antiquated technology, and are difficult to repair. Such hardware also limits Instructors' ability to insert and remove effective training faults. This paper describes a design concept which provides a robust training test set, including hardware, for operators to learn basic troubleshooting skills and ATE interaction. The US Navy recognized the benefits of such a system to address training deficiencies and initiated the development and acquisition of the CASS Training Set (CATS). The test set includes a variety of training scenarios which are commonly seen in the fleet, including digital tests, analog tests, Operational Flight Program (OFP) loads, alignments, Radio Frequency (RF) tests, diagnostics, etc. The CATS training UUT uses latching relays to induce consistent, repeatable hardware faults, and a microcontroller to produce software faults. Faults are applied and removed through the Test Program Set (TPS) and require no soldering or de-soldering of components. This process automates training fault insertion, extends the life of the training equipment, and provides repeatable fault signatures. Consistent training scenarios ensure lower variance in technical capabilities of course graduates. A complete hardware and software package with the look-and-feel of a fleet avionics asset, but the reliability to withstand a training environment provides a valuable tool to train ATE operators and should be a basic part of any ATE system.

Keywords: *Automated Test Equipment, Unit Under Test, Test Program Set, Consolidated Automated Support System*

I. HISTORY

During Autotestcon 2007, Amadeo Roybal from the United States Marine Corps Automated Test Equipment Program in Albany, GA presented a training device which could simulate basic card capabilities including flip flops, decoders, BCD counters, diodes, rectifiers, etc. [1]. Training scenarios would induce faults via switching relays and walk the operator through probing instructions to isolate the faulty component. In 2010, NAVAIR PMAs 205 and 260 approached the TPS development team in Jacksonville, FL about developing a

similar, but more complex training device for the Navy. The Center for Naval Aviation Technical Training Units (CNATTU) in Miramar and Oceana had been struggling for years with failing assets used in their training classes. As a result, the quality of ATE technicians graduating had been declining. The solution was to develop an inexpensive training TPS, including UUT, which could insert repeatable faults without risk of damage from soldering and de-soldering components. Such a TPS had to be robust enough to withstand the daily abuses of newly trained sailors while providing the same look, feel, and capability of what will be experienced in the fleet. Thus CATS was born.

Figure 1. CATS Hardware – Consisting of an interface device (ID), UUT, D38999 style cables, cable adapters, RF cables, extender cards, safety cover, and case.

II. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

1. 3A1 (RF CCA)

The 3A1 CCA contains a wideband 400-1300 MHz +8dBm voltage controlled oscillator (VCO) and mixer for generating continuous wave and chirped RF pulses. The VCO is driven by a 16 bit monotonic digital-to-analog converter (DAC) on the 3A4 card. The VCO output is switched to directly drive the +17dBm max power output amplifier or drive into the mixer. If driving the mixer, the

signal is mixed with an input RF signal from the ATE and then output to the amplifier. Frequencies are restricted to the band centered on 462.6 MHz. This was chosen to reduce the EMI effects of higher frequencies with short cable runs.

The 3A1 also contains a stand alone 3-to-8 decoder circuit, SGMA wrap back, EEPROM, and dual tuning pot circuit. The 3-to-8 decoder is used to show how pins stuck hi, low, or open affect the fault signature of bit walk tests. The SGMA wraps signals generated from the ATE back to the ATE to verify. If the signal path breaks, the fault signature will be a change in the angle measured. The dual tuning pot circuit is used to introduce the operator to using pot tweakers and TPS adjustment routines. Eight fault inducing relays exist as well as an SPI EEPROM for bus faults.

Figure 2. 3A1 functional diagram

2. 3A2 (Analog CCA)

The 3A2 allows students to probe various stages of an opamp circuit and oscillator circuit. The opamp circuit is a two stage opamp. The first stage is driven by the 3A4 DAC and is inverted with a gain of 3. The second stage then sums that signal with an input from the ATE or oscillator. The result is again inverted with a gain of 2. Probe points are provided along the path to allow students to practice probing instructions and understand basic opamp circuit performance. Faults include changing gain, opamp railing, power rail faults, etc.

Figure 3. 3A2 opamp circuit

The oscillator circuit is a Wein bridge opamp circuit with two clipping diodes (LEDs) to force loop gain to 3. A potentiometer is used to adjust oscillation frequency and magnitude (higher frequency produces clipping). A second stage opamp is used as a buffer and shifts the

oscillation voltage into the required range for the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and VCO. Four fault inducing relays exist as well as an SPI EEPROM for bus faults.

Figure 4. 3A2 oscillator circuit

3. 3A3 (Expansion Slot)

A blank 80 pin CCA slot is included on the motherboard to support any future capabilities that will be added. All power and signals are brought out to that connector – Including 10 spare I/O pins that run to the microcontroller and 15 spare pins that run to the UUT's external J2 connector.

4. 3A4 (Digital CCA)

The 3A4 contains the brain of the UUT, an Atmel Atmega2560 microcontroller. The Atmega2560 is an 8-bit RISC processor running at 16MHz with 256KB on-board flash for storing firmware. It also features 4KB EEPROM and 8KB internal SRAM. The capabilities of the microcontroller that are used are the ADC, PWM, Timer/Counters, SPI interface, USART, watchdog timer, and power-on reset. The microcontroller commands and monitors all aspects of the UUT operation as well as interfacing with the ATE via RS232. Instructions are sent from the ATE to the UUT to perform an action. The action may be to break a relay, or output an invalid signal.

Also on the 3A4 is a 16 bit monolithic DAC, a MAX232 RS232 level shifter, a single pot tuning circuit, and status LEDs. The Atmega2560 has 86 programmable I/O lines which provide direct interface to digital test pins from the ATE as well as controlling all fault inducing relays in the UUT. The 3A4 provides most analog stimulus via the DAC which controls the 3A2 opamp circuit and the 3A1 VCO. Three fault inducing relays exist as well as a separate SPI EEPROM for bus faults.

5. 3A5 (Motherboard)

All CCAs in the UUT plug into a motherboard which routes signals from each CCAs edge connector out to the appropriate chassis components or the external connectors J1-J4. All CCA connectors offer very high reliability with 100k mate/demate cycles. They also feature guide pins and shielding to protect the pins from damage. The motherboard is a 6 layer board with 3 fault inducing relays.

6. Chassis Components

The chassis components consist of an RF mixer, RF amplifier, bit test indicator (BTI), elapsed time indicator (ETI), EMI filter, DC/DC converter, temperature sensor and associated circuitry, signature resistor, power resistor, and fuse. The chassis circuitry is provided to create complex callout groups for the student to troubleshoot.

7. Chassis Frame

The chassis is built out of an aluminum frame with shielded gasket to contain spurious EMI transmitted from within the UUT. Aluminum mounting plates are provided for chassis components. Machined Delrin was used to fabricate the card guides/extractor. This maximizes durability and minimizes wear on the cards during repeated CCA insertion/ejection cycles.

8. RF Cables

RF connections are made from the UUT to the ATE. SMA style connectors were chosen to train the operator how to use torque wrenches when working with delicate RF connectors. SMA-SMA and SMA-N cables are used

to expose the operator to a variety of what is common on fleet assets.

Prior to running any RF tests, TPSs usually perform path loss compensation calculations on each cable. Because each cable has different losses at different frequencies, the TPS compensates for the losses of a specific cable during a specific test. If the operator connects a visually identical cable, the losses of that cable will not be compensated for correctly and the test might fail. To prevent this; the operator is trained to follow directions when hooking up similar looking cables. The CATS cables are distinguished by attenuators of differing values. These attenuators have heat shrink applied to make each cable visually identical. This allows the TPS to determine if the operator has correctly followed directions connecting the required cable. If not, a warning message is displayed and the instructor can emphasize the need to remain vigilant and follow directions.

9. Functional Block Diagram

Figure 5. CATS functional block diagram

10. Student Schematic vs. Instructor Schematic

To maintain the illusion of a real UUT, the fault inducing relays are hidden from the student. Although the component will obviously be visible on the card, the PCB traces are all run on internal layers to make tracing signals more difficult and all provided drawings and schematics have the relays absent. An example of the student schematic vs. instructor schematic is given in the figure below.

Figure 6. Student schematic vs. Instructor schematic

III. FAULT MODES

Fault insertion is accomplished by the TPS prompting the instructor to enter a fault code at the beginning of the TPS. The instructor enters a four digit code in the format XX. Where, X's are don't cares and correspond to the desired fault. For example, to implement training scenario 14, the operator can enter code 1384 or 1204. This method makes it difficult for the student to determine which training scenario is being run and reduces the likelihood of students sharing solutions with their peers.

After the code has been entered, the ATE coordinates with the UUT to set relays, or modify signals to induce the desired faulty behavior. The fault remains with the UUT until a new fault code is applied. Similarly, all faults are easily removed and the UUT is made RFI by simply entering fault code 00. This system allows instructors to rapidly insert and remove faults – freeing up more time for instruction.

A. Fault Difficulty

1. Crawl: Easy fault with small primary cause of failure (PCOF)
2. Walk: More difficult components, larger PCOF to down-select from
3. Run: Wrong PCOF, ID failure, complex UUT faults

The CATS program provides 80 total scenarios with approximately 19 crawl, 42 walk, and 19 run faults.

B. Fault Types

1. ID faults: A relay board inside the ID physically breaks or modifies a connection.
2. Cable faults: Cable adapters are connected to the cables. Adapters have predefined faults built in.
3. UUT software controlled hard faults: Relay induced faults, where a relay is physically switched to cause the fault.

4. UUT software faults: The microcontroller outputs an incorrect signal to cause failure in a particular part of the circuit.
5. TPS misdirection: The TPS provides stimulus which is incorrect for the test being performed.

C. Training Scenario Examples

- Fault 31 (crawl / software fault)

This is an example of how a basic training scenario works.

The 3A4 will not output any value on the data lines. Values will be stuck at low. The PCOF will be the 3A4 card. The instructor will enter a code to set the ID/UUT to ready for issue (RFI) condition. This simulates the instructor repairing the 3A4 card. The operator will rerun the TPS and the end-to-end (ETE) will pass.

Figure 7. Training Scenario 31 Flowchart

- Fault 16 (run / hardware fault)

This is an example of how a cable fault training scenario might work.

The instructor will swap the students cable adapter 2A1 (S/N MBK131) with 2A1 (S/N MEB283). Cable adapter 2A1:P1 (S/N MEB283) is incorrectly pinned with pin 10 moved to the pin 11 hole. The PCOF will be the 3A4 card. The instructor will enter a code to maintain the same fault scenario. This simulates the instructor repairing the 3A4 card, but the problem remains. The operator will rerun the TPS and the same failure will occur. The instructor will suggest ohming out the connection (UUT, cables, ID). The operator will then notice that the wire should be in pin 10 but instead, a mistake was made and it was put in pin 11 instead. The instructor will acknowledge the correct solution and return the good adapter 2A1 (S/N MBK131). The operator will rerun the TPS and the ETE will pass.

Figure 8. Training Scenario 16 Flowchart

- Fault 23 (walk / software controlled hard fault)

This is an example of how a bus fault might be detected in our training scenarios.

Each card contains an EEPROM. The EEPROMs are all connected together via a bus. The instructor will enter a code to cause a fault on one of the bus lines of card 3A1. The fault will pull the bus line to GND, causing the TPS to fail. The TPS will enter diagnostics and attempt to isolate which card is faulty by instructing the operator to remove each card one at a time and rerun the test. When the diagnostics test passes, the card that was last removed was holding the bus low and thus faulty. The operator removes 3A2. Rerun fails showing the line still pulled to GND. The operator removes A1. Rerun will pass. PCOF is the 3A1. The operator will indicate the 3A1 as the cause of failure. The instructor will enter a code to set the ID/UUT to RFI condition. This simulates the instructor repairing the 3A1 card. The operator will rerun the TPS and the ETE will pass.

- Fault 58 (walk / software fault)

This is an example of how extender cards are used in our training scenarios.

The instructor will enter a code to cause the 3A4 card to not send an enable signal to the 3A1. The ATE will input a digital signal and receive no digital response, causing the TPS to fail. The ATE will attempt to determine whether the fault is on the 3A1 card which contains the 3-to-8 decoder circuitry or on the 3A4 card which enables that circuitry. Diagnostics tests will have the operator remove 3A1, insert an extender card, and attach the safety cover. The function of the extender card is to allow probing of the 3A5 (motherboard) connector. The operator holds a probe

to the enable line and reruns the test. If the enable signal is present, then the 3A1 is faulty, if it is not present then the 3A4 is faulty. In this training scenario, the 3A4 card does not send the enable signal (this simulates a faulty 3A4). PCOF is the 3A4. The operator will indicate the 3A4 as the cause of failure. The instructor will enter a code to set the ID/UUT to RFI condition. This simulates the instructor repairing the 3A4 card. The operator will rerun the TPS and the ETE will pass.

- Fault 15 (run / software controlled hard fault)

This is an example of how an ID fault training scenario might work.

The instructor will enter a code to activate a relay on the ID CCA and break the pulse line between the UUT and ATE wave form digitizer (WFRD). The PCOF will be the 3A4 card. The instructor will enter a code to maintain the same fault scenario. This simulates the instructor repairing the 3A4 card, but the problem remains. The operator will rerun the TPS and the same failure will occur. The instructor will suggest to the operator to ohm out the connection (UUT, cables, ID). The operator will then trace the problem to the broken ID wire, not supplying the 5VDC pulse from the UUT to the ATE. The instructor will enter a code to set the ID/UUT to RFI condition. This simulates the instructor repairing the ID. The operator will rerun the TPS and the end-to-end (ETE) will pass.

Note: The instructor has flexibility to adjust to the capability level of the student. In this training scenario, the instructor may have the student ohm out the connection path as was just described. The instructor may also have the student simply run ID self test to validate the ID as a way to isolate the problem. Teaching remains up to the instructor. The CATS program simply provides a standardized tool to aid in their effort.

- Test Workaround Procedure (TWP)

Test workaround procedures are common in the fleet. They are temporary solutions to work around TPS problems before an official release fixes the issue. TWPs are typically stored as hardcopy printouts at repair sites. Operators must learn to check the TWP folder before declaring a part faulty. The test limits may have changed, or the PCOF order may be different, thus requiring a different course of action. CATS provides a TWP for test 1200 which changes the PCOF order from 3A2, 3A4, PS1 to 3A4, 3A2, PS1. When the operator fails test 1200, they should check to see if a TWP exists for that fault. If the operator checks the TWP, they will realize the correct failure is the 3A4. If the operator does not check the TWP, they will incorrectly state the 3A2 as the failure. This will then be a teaching point for the instructor to emphasize the need to check for TWPs before sending off a part for repair.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Roybal, "Training Solution For Automated Test Equipment Marine Corps Electronic Testing," Autotestcon 2007.